

A new evolution theory model for the histo-blood group ABO genes

Once unicellular life transformed into multicellular organisms, an adequate system to transport oxygen, nutrients and waste became essential. In simple life forms like sponges, sea anemones and jelly fish the surface tissue is thin enough to allow direct oxygen diffusion, but in more complex animals circulating blood is responsible for the distribution of gasses to cells (Millar & Ratcliffe, 1989). The evolution of blood itself -connective tissue of liquid plasma and cells- remains controversial, but the oldest fossil with a cardiovascular system has been estimated to be 520-million-year-old (Ma, Cong, Hou, Edgecombe, & Strausfeld, 2014). The emergence of blood cells probably preceded this event, with respiratory proteins evolving before the blood cells. The mammal respiratory protein hemoglobin is believed to have originated 450 million years ago (Hardison, 1998). Anucleate blood cells carrying hemoglobin, like the human erythrocytes, might have appeared 160 million years ago (Soslau, 2020). Erythrocytes are the most abundant cells in the human body and a recent study has also associated these red blood cells with a role in the innate immune system (Anderson, Brodsky, & Mangalmurti, 2018). Moreover, red blood cells feature the surface carbohydrate antigens A, B, and H, which are clinically relevant for blood transfusions and organ transplants. Additionally, histo-blood ABO polymorphism has also been associated with host defense strategies against infectious agents (Anstee, 2010; Geisel, Steuer, Ko, & Beuth, 1995; Stowell & Stowell, 2019).

The human ABO genetic locus encodes for two glycosyltransferases (GTs), which both use an α 1,3-linkage to catalyze the binding of a specific sugar to H substances. The A transferase has a substrate specificity for N-acetyl-D-galactosamine (GalNAc), and B transferase is specific for D-galactose (Gal). H substances need enzymatic catalyzation by α 1,2-fucosyltransferases (FTs) for their synthesis. The encoding genes are FUT1, FUT2 and SEC1, where both FUT1 and FUT2/SEC1 produce functional α 1,2-FTs, but they have different acceptor substrate specificity. SEC1 is considered a pseudogene and FUT2 often exhibits as a null allele. When no α 1,2-FTs are present, no H antigens are produced, and subsequently the A/B transferases will not be functional either (i.e. expression of the O allele).

ABO genes are also present in other vertebrate species, but show different patterns of ABH antigens expression (Kominato et al., 1992). The human histo-blood group ABO knows over 250 alleles and is intensively studied for its polymorphism.

Previous studies were in favor of the convergent evolution theory to explain the primate ABO polymorphism (O'Huigin, Sato, & Klein, 1997; Saitou & Yamamoto, 1997), but more recent research indicated trans-species evolution (Segurel et al., 2012). Lalueza-Fox et al. (2008) demonstrated that ABO polymorphism was established before the split of humans and Neanderthals. The study by Yamamoto et al. (2014) is mostly discussed in this essay, and challenges both the convergent and trans-species evolution theories. Furthermore, the study provides evidence of early A/B polymorphism, shortly after the separation of fish and amphibians.

The group of Yamamoto & Hakomori (1990) previously elucidated four amino acid substitutions at position 176, 235, 266 and 268 in the ABO gene location, which would account for the differences between the A and the B transferases. A single nucleotide deletion at position 261, or a Gly268Arg substitution were indicated to cause the O allele. In addition, four additional GTs are encoded by GGTW1, A3GALT2, GBGT1 and GLT6D1 genes in humans. The first three are evolutionary related to the ABO locus, and they all connect GalNAc/Gal via an α 1,3-glycosidic bond to substances other than

the H substrate (Haslam & Baenziger, 1996; Keusch, Manzella, Nyame, Cummings, & Baenziger, 2000; Larsen et al., 1989).

Based on animal genome databases, Yamamoto and colleagues (2014) constructed a phylogenetic tree for the α 1,3-GTs. This resulted in separate clusters for the GGTW1, A3GALT2, GBGT1 and GLT6D1 genes, but the A and B transferases formed a single cluster, as shown in figure 1. A model for birth-and-death evolution (Eirin-Lopez, Rebordinos, Rooney, & Rozas, 2012; Turcot-Dubois et al., 2007) seems to be applicable for the Gal(NAc)-GT genes. For example; the frog *Xenopus tropicalis* contains the ABO genes, but lacks the other GTs, and all birds that were examined only possessed the GBGT1 gene (table 1).

Analyses on phylogeny and chromosomal location suggest original emergence of the FUT2 gene, followed by duplication, allowing FUT1 to arise and acquire novel characteristics. SEC1 must have originated from a later duplication of FUT2 (table 1).

Noteworthy is the fact that all examined fish genomes lack α 1,2-FTs and ABO genes, while *Xenopus tropicalis* contains four FUT2 and multiple ABO gene sequences. Since many mammals and the Chinese softshell turtle possess α 1,2-FTs and A/B transferases, it is much likely the A/B antigens appeared after the separation of the fish and amphibian lineages in evolution.

Previous studies showed that the 3rd and 4th amino acid substitution loci (266 and 268) in the ABO gene are crucial for the sugar substrate specificity of the A and B transferases, whereas the first (176) and the second (235) seem to play a less important role (Patenaude et al., 2002; Yamamoto & Hakomori, 1990; Yamamoto & McNeill, 1996).

The group of Yamamoto et al. (2014) conducted a sophisticated *in vitro* mutagenesis study to reassess these findings; 40 amino acid substitution constructs on human A transferase were synthesized, of which each of the 20 possible amino acid substitutions were combined with either glycine of A transferase at codon 266, or with alanine of B transferase at codon 268. The anticipated LGG and MGA motifs for specificity of human A and B alleles, respectively, served as control constructs. Extra constructs were generated for codons 263-268, which are known to exist as ABO and GalNAc/Gal α 1,3-GTs polymorphisms in nature.

HeLa cells (expressing H substances) were transfected with the constructs and subsequently examined for A/B antigen expression by using antibodies (table 2). Indeed, residues at locus 266 proved to be crucial for sugar specificity determination of the encoded transferase. Since a few constructs with glycine at codon 268 expressed different sugar specificity than with alanine, this locus must also be influential. As is evident from table 2; some constructs allow combined transferase activity, whereas others result in no activity. Unexpectedly, glycine at codon 267 seems to be a pre-requisite for combined A/B transferase activity.

Yamamoto et al. (2014) further used their table to identify A/B specificity of individual ABO genes in various species, which possess corresponding gene duplications. As mentioned earlier, *Xenopus tropicalis* contains multiple copies of the ABO gene, and it was demonstrated that the frog exclusively has an A transferase gene sequence with AGG and TGC motif and a B transferase gene with MAA motif. Similar findings were observed in other species and it makes a hypothesis highly probable where functional differentiation between A and B transferase genes appeared early after the ABO gene emergence in amphibians.

In continuation of their phylogenetic analysis, Yamamoto et al. (2014) discovered that many species have non-allelic ABO protein sequences, opposed to the human ABO allelic system. The majority of the ABO proteins clustered in species-specific groups, including the retro-pseudogenes. The

phylogenetic tree, as established by the group of Yamamoto et al. (2014), suggests that the original sequence may have contained a TGA motif, since it was exclusively observed in the retro-pseudogenes of the examined animal species. Interestingly, this motif is present in some bacterial ABO genes.

ABO specificity is mostly found in Gram negative bacteria, which form the largest population in the human intestinal tract (Springer, 1970). Since ABO genes are absent in many invertebrates, plants and fungi, horizontal gene transfer between eukaryotes and prokaryotes seems a logical explanation (Brew, Tumbale, & Acharya, 2010). Yamamoto et al. (2014) identified 56 bacterial ABO gene and constructed a phylogenetic tree from these data. The tree showed two distinct clusters, namely A transferase genes with GalNAc specificity and a group with B and A/B transferase genes specific for Gal and GalNAc/gal, respectively. Besides the TGA motif solely shared with animal retro-pseudogenes, a seemingly unique bacterial QGG motif was identified.

The assignment of A/B specificity to the separate ABO gene sequences (table 2) made it plausible to study the AO polymorphism. This is useful, since multiple inactivation mechanisms have been identified in humans (Yamamoto et al., 1993), but these seem to differ from mechanisms in other primates and non-primate animals with AO alleles. Thus, O polymorphisms show species-specific patterns, and to ratify this observation, Yamamoto et al. (2014) were able to indicate two SNPs which were likely to cause AO polymorphism in dogs.

Reflecting back on existing hypotheses on ABO polymorphisms, Yamamoto and colleagues (2014) considered the motifs in table 2. This table shows that the A-B conversion does not necessarily need to be the result of a change from LGG to MGA motif, but can also arise from other amino acid substitutions. With a single substitution several motifs can change to become B specific (EGG, HGG, YGG). On the contrary, the change from LGG to a B specific motif needs at least two nucleotide changes. This makes the convergence theory unlikely, since it should have happened many times in the evolution of primates, without strong selection pressure when other substitutions create the same functionality. Therefore, Yamamoto et al. (2014) propose that A and B alleles were both present in the common ancestor of primates and ABO polymorphism later resulted from species-specific molecular mechanisms.

In conclusion; A/B transferase gene appeared after the separation of fish and amphibian lineages and the animal A and B transferase genes did not evolve in two separate genetic entities. The reason behind the A/B dependency remains obscure, but possibilities could be proximity in genetic distance and sharing of the same substrate substance. However, SEC1 and FUT2 genes have this in common, but those took independent evolutionary paths. A consideration where the A and B locus are placed in tandem, could be an explanation for a multigenic to unigenic transition.

Yamamoto et al. (2014) propose species-specific sequence homology through intragenic exchanges from the common ancestral A/B genes instead of convergent evolution to explain ABO polymorphism. Although some convergent evolution in motifs may have occurred, the prototypic alleles derive from the LGG (A transferase) and MGA (B transferase) motifs, and are shared by the common ancestor of primates.

ABO polymorphism evolved in some species by carrying multiple gene copies, but in primates the polymorphism is due to unigenic alleles. In the multigenic case, many copies are partial, nonfunctional genes, which may serve as reservoir for genetic diversity.

ABO polymorphism may have an important role in antimicrobial defense. A/B antigens are more expressed on cells of the intestinal tract than on red blood cells. There is high interaction of cell surface sugars with microbes in the intestinal lining. Both functional A and B transferases may have

been disadvantageous to protect the body from infections, whereas different ABO polymorphisms could have an inhibiting effect on microbe invasion. The two separate A/B gene clusters in bacteria suggest independent A and B gene evolution in the prokaryotes, and it probably serves to mimic the animal ABO system for better survival chance. Horizontal gene transfer allows quick adaptation to the host defense system, but intra-species ABO polymorphism could have triggered the host's defense by changing allele frequency (Seymour, Allan, Pomiankowski, & Gustafsson, 2004).

Although a few questions remain unanswered, the extensive research by Yamamoto et al. (2014) provides important knowledge about evolutionary trends, and could potentially serve the medical field in better understanding of blood transfusion, organ transplant rejections, or to generate models for infectious diseases. With the extension of genome databasing, missing links may be added to the picture created by the research group. Their work proved how phylogenetic analyses from genomic sequencing, combined with chromosomal location and *in vitro* studies can result in detailed insight in evolution of genes and proteins, thus forming an example of high-quality research in this field.

Figure 1. α 1,3-Gal(NAc) transferase family of genes. The yellow ABO cluster clearly separates from the other α 1,3-Gal(NAc) transferase clusters. *Figure retrieved from Yamamoto et al. (2014)*

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Table 1

Species	Ensembl Database	α1.2-FT Genes			α1.3-Ga(Naβ) Genes			GBG1T	ABO/GBG1T Ancient	ASGALT2	GGTAT(-1)	GGTAT(-2)	GLT801(-1)	GLT801(-2)					
		SECT1	FUT2	FUT1	ABO	Pseudo Ancient	ABO												
Human	ENSG	232871	176920	174951	270524	IGA	175164	LGG	148228	GGA		184389	HAA	204136	HAA		204007	GNL	
Chimpanzee	ENSPTRG	N/A	11251	11256			N/A	MGA	21510	GGA							29002	GSL	
Gorilla	ENSGGOG	232871	1238	1245			11353	MGA	3448	GGA		3596	HAA				7957	GSL	
Orangutan	ENSPPYG	10210		10213			N/A	LGG	19724	GGA		1574	HAA				19761	GSL	
Gibbon	ENSNLEG	4592	4601	18767			N/A	LGG									8630	GSL	
Macaque	ENSMMLUG			4020	3828	TGA	15100	MGA	15277	GGA		3288	HAA				21493	GSL	
Marmoset	ENSCJAG	19738					N/A	LGG	N/A	GGA		1190	HAA	20186	HAA		13615	DGS	
Tarsier	ENSTSYG		23164				17944	LGG						7103	HKV		14590	DGS	
Mouse Lemur	ENSMICG			5965			12209	MGA	10686	GGA				16109	HAA			DGS	
Bushbaby	ENSOQAG	29739	3567	24452	27171	TGA	17928	SGA	29130	GAA		34743	HAA	1891	HAA		28660	HGA	
Tree Shrew	ENSTBEG				33703	TGA	29319	LGG									30414	DGS	
Rabbit	ENSOJUG	27963	27542	17168	27379	TEA	8654	LGG	10198	GGA		11627	HAA	3735	HAA		12485	HST	
					21195	TEA	17014	MGA				12461	HAP	3469	HAA		28538	HGA	
					26524	IGA	17844	MGA											
					27881	IGA	7815	IGA											
Pika	ENSOPRG	40364	56978	8461	3647	TGA	15984	IGA				6196	HAA				1107	---	
Mouse	ENSMUSG	21014	21011	20995			15787	GGA	28828	GGA		28784	HAA	36778	HAA		26882	HRA	
Rat	ENSRNOG						38908	AGG				5935	HAA	19179	HAA		42373	HSA	
							48988	MGA											
							50908	MGA											
							45801	MGA											
Kangaroo Rat	ENSDORG			1233			6088	MGA	11384	GGA		12439	HAA				7878	GSS	
Guinea Pig	ENSCPOG	20316	7337	6070			4874	GGA	4874	GGA		3018	HAA	14621	HAA		2951	GDT	
Squirrel	ENSTTOG	23913	12296	12334			24594	HAA				44093	HAA	5448	HAA		25973	GGS	
Dolphin	ENSTRG		8204	14561			14438	GGA	14438	GGA		856	HAA	12090	HAA		38201	HSA	
Cow	ENSBTAG	14514	21557	23374			30318	GRA						5518	HAA		20248	DGA	
Pig	ENSSSCG	27384	3145	3141			N/A	AGG									5758	DGA	
Horse	ENSECAG	5681	5862	6058			14463	MGA	12442	GGA				22868	HAA		8592	DSA	
Cat	ENSFCAG		5993		4986	TGA	20130	AGG	12442	GGA		3576	HTA	30534	HAA		21425	HAA	
			22344	27868	5049	TGA	25873	AGG	24387	GGA		7288	HAA	845	HAA		22798	QSA	
Panda	ENSAMEG	14807	19834	19826			7867	MGP										11754	DGS
					19214	IGA	1006	MGA										3338	DGA
							1485	---											
Ferret	ENSMPUG	3823	18965	3721			12419	AGG	12426	GGA		15083	HAA	7373	HAA		7470	---	
							13012	IGA											
							1985	MEA											
Dog	ENSCAFG	23807	32038		7214	IGA	19757	AGG	19864	GGA		10375	HAA	20295	HAA		29005	DGS	
					24235	AGA	24143	SGG				23219	HAA	12248	HAA				
Microbat	ENSMLUG	6325	23144	6348			26173	LGG											
			27047				9519	MGA											
Megabat	ENSPVAG								1029	GGA		15028	HAA						
Hedgehog	ENSEEUG			11062			6261	TGG	14255	GGA		13948	HAA	13477	HAA				
Shrew	ENSLAFG	28837	2891	3064	29560	TGF						5495	HAA	28653	HAA		15846	HSA	
Elephant	ENSLAFG			12789			10293	AGG	5688	GGA							7432	HSA	
Hyrax	ENSPCAG		1114	1320			12074	AGG	15668	GGA		5305	HAA						
L. Hedgehog Tenrec	ENSETEG		17392				9122	TGS	11094	GGA		139	HAA				18207	GNG	
Armadillo	ENSDNCG			5189					898	GGA									
Sloth	ENSCHOG		7931						2851	GGA								10340	DGA
																		2110	DGS

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(I). G at codon 268				(II). A at codon 268				(III). Additional			
Codons	A	B	A/B	Codons	A	B	A/B	Codons	A	B	A/B
(266–268)	Activity	Activity	Specificity	(266–268)	Activity	Activity	Specificity	(266–268)	Activity	Activity	Specificity
AGG	+++++	–	A	AGA	+++++	++	AB	AAA	+++++	–	A
CGG	+++++	–	A	CGA	++++	+++	AB	AAN	–	–	–
DGG	++	++	AB	DGA	–	+++	B	AAS	++++	+++	AB
EGG	++++	–	A	EGA	–	++++	B	MAA	–	+++++	B
FGG	–	++++	B	FGA	–	++++	B	MGP	–	+++	B
GGG	++++	–	A	GGA	++++	+++	AB	MGS	–	+++++	B
HGG	–	++++	B	HGA	–	++++	B	QGC	–	+++++	B
IGG	++++	++++	AB	IGA	–	++++	B	SSE	–	–	–
KGG	–	–	–	KGA	–	+++	B	TAS	–	–	–
LGG	+++++	–	A	LGA	+++++	+	AB	TEA	–	–	–
MGG	++++	++++	AB	MGA	–	++++	B	TGC	++++	–	A
NGG	+++++	+	AB	NGA	++++	++	AB	TGF	–	–	–
PGG	+++++	–	A	PGA	++++	–	A	TSE	–	–	–
QGG	++++	+++	AB	QGA	–	+++++	B				
RGG	–	–	–	RGA	–	–	–	(263–268)			
SGG	++++	–	A	SGA	++++	+++	AB	AVYGS	–	–	–
TGG	+++++	–	A	TGA	++++	+++	AB	FYFTSE	–	–	–
VGG	++++	–	A	VGA	++++	+++	AB	HYYMGG	++++	++++	AB
WGG	++	+	AB	WGA	–	++++	B	YYYAGG	+++++	–	A
YGG	–	++++	B	YGA	–	++	B	YYMGG	+++++	+++	AB
								YYTGS	+++++	–	A
								YYTSE	–	–	–
								YYTSG	+++++	–	A

Table 2. Specificity and activity of human A transferase expression constructs. *Table retrieved from Yamamoto et al. (2014)*

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